

Impact Study

Children's Health

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Context

The fight against diseases in children, including cancer, is an endeavour that touches the very heart of our society's future. As children represent the next generation, their health is directly linked to the overall well-being and progress of our communities.

Combating diseases in children is not just about saving lives; it's about preserving the potential for innovation, creativity and leadership that each child holds. Early intervention and treatment can prevent long-term complications, reduce healthcare costs and improve quality of life, enabling children to thrive and contribute meaningfully to society as they grow up.

The above would not be possible without biodata resources.. The case studies below illustrate ways in which biodata resources have been enabling improved health outcomes for children.

Beating childhood cancer

The power of digital infrastructure and datasets is evident in the dramatic improvements in childhood cancer five-year survival rates, for example [from 60% in 1970 to over 85% as of 2020 in the USA, and from 40% to 85% in the UK over the same period](#). Initiatives like the [Childhood Cancer Data Initiative \(CCDI\)](#) are enabling researchers and medical professionals to share and use childhood cancer data, connecting it with the necessary infrastructure to facilitate collaboration. For example, their [Childhood Cancer Data Catalog](#) serves as a comprehensive directory of paediatric oncology data resources. It encompasses a wide range of assets, such as childhood cancer repositories, registries, programs, knowledgebases, analytic tools and catalogues that either handle or reference data. Significant examples of resources listed in the Catalog include the [Childhood Cancer Model Atlas \(CCMA\)](#) – the largest collection of high-risk paediatric solid tumour cell lines in the world – and the [Automated Childhood Cancer Information System \(ACCIS\)](#) – an authoritative source of data on cancer incidence and survival of children and adolescents in Europe and coordinated and financially supported by the [International Agency for Research on Cancer](#).

Additionally, the high rate of participation in clinical trials developed by paediatric cooperative groups like the [Children's Oncology Group \(COG\)](#) is playing an important role. With [over 50% of children](#) diagnosed with cancer enrolled in trials organised by COG or other cooperative groups, researchers have been able to learn and advance therapies in a consistent and prospective manner. This stands in contrast to the adult oncology field, where fewer than 5% of patients are enrolled in trials. The uniform data collection and sharing made possible by this type of collaborative effort, which includes research infrastructure, has been a key driver of progress.

Overall, the rapidly increasing knowledge of the molecular and [genomic bases of cancers](#), enabled by decreasing costs of genomic sequencing technologies and the development of new bioinformatic methods to analyse large datasets, has led to the development of [precision therapies](#) that target the effects of tumour-specific mutations. Resources like the

[Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance \(AVE\)](#) are important in this context. AVE systematically maps the impact of genetic variants on functional elements in the human genome, enabling a better understanding of the specific effects of tumour-associated variants at the nucleotide level. This allows for more targeted and personalised cancer therapies: by interpreting the functional consequences of genetic variants identified through genomic sequencing, AVE's variant effect maps help guide treatment decisions for cancer patients by distinguishing pathogenic variants from benign or uncertain ones.

[Recent research](#) confirms that the data obtained from DNA and RNA analysis can be integrated with traditional pathology methods (such as examining tissue samples under a microscope) to achieve a more comprehensive and accurate diagnosis. When these genetic and clinical data are shared within the medical and research community, they can help other patients by providing insights into similar cases. This data sharing also supports future research and discoveries that may improve diagnosis, treatment and outcomes for other patients.

Creating safe medicines

The development of new drugs often requires the testing of interactions between different pharmaceutical ingredients. On top of the usual safeguards, [children's medicine](#) requires additional in-depth assessment: to help address this challenge and provide global access to toxicity information of excipients (non-active ingredients) for paediatric medicine, the [Safety and Toxicity of Excipients for Paediatrics \(STEP\)](#) database was launched in 2014.

As of 2022, STEP has around 3,000 registered users in 44 different countries, with the pharmaceutical industry representing 70% of its user base. The [European Medicines Agency](#), a regulatory body, has been closely involved in the database's development, and other prominent organisations such as the Gates Foundation have taken a close interest, for example by providing funding to support additional excipients for inclusion.

The database has become a valuable resource for accelerating product development, optimising staff efficiency and ensuring patient safety on a global scale and particularly within the EU. The STEP database has been cited by major pharmaceutical companies, such as Pfizer, Roche, GSK and Novartis in the creation and testing of new drugs. Proveca, a pharmaceutical company that develops and commercialises medicines for children, used STEP to screen 50 excipients in 12 formulation development programmes, which saved the company around £1 million and 12 months of development time. This included contributing to the approval of Sialanar, a treatment for excessive and severe drooling.

Conclusions

The case studies presented here demonstrate the transformative power of data and collaboration in the fields of childhood cancer and paediatric medicine. By leveraging digital infrastructure and datasets, researchers and medical professionals have been able to make significant strides in improving survival rates, developing precision therapies and ensuring the safety of medicines for children.

However, the work is far from over. Ever-more-complex approaches will need to be run on growing volumes of data, and innovative applications leveraging [artificial intelligence](#) will become commonplace for diagnosis, classification and treatment planning. Increased investment in and expansion of digital infrastructure, coupled with continued collaboration, will be essential to harness the full potential of data-driven innovations in paediatric healthcare that create and maintain a healthier future for children around the world.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
Automated Childhood Cancer Information System (AACIS)	The AACIS is a platform which hosts data on cancer incidence and survival of children and adolescents in Europe between the years 1991-2010. It collects data from more than 50 population-based cancer registries in 19 European countries to analyse temporal trends and geographical patterns in children and adolescents.
Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance (AVE)	<p>The AVE is a collaboration which aims to advance the promise of the Human Genome Project by interpreting the landscape of human genetic variation. It is building an atlas of the impact of all possible sequence variants for disease-related functional elements. They are particularly interested in multiplexed assays of variant effects (MAVEs) which can be used to assess thousands of variants simultaneously.</p> <p>They support a number of resources including MaveDB, the MAVE registry, MAVE impute, MAVE pipelines and a list of Variant Effect Predictors.</p>
Childhood Cancer Data Catalog	The Childhood Cancer Data Catalog is a database of paediatric data resources for sharing clinical and research data related to childhood cancer. It is run by the National Cancer Institute as part of the Childhood Cancer Data Initiative.
Childhood Cancer Data Initiative (CCDI)	The CCDI is a community of resources to advance understanding of childhood cancer biology to improve diagnosis, treatment, quality of life and survivorship. These resources include the Child Cancer Clinical Data Commons, the Childhood Cancer Data Catalog, the Molecular Targets Platform and the NCCR Explorer.
Childhood Cancer Model Atlas (CCMA)	The CCMA is a collection of cell lines for high risk paediatric solid tumours, with detailed information regarding their genetics, biology and behaviours. It hosts a total of 573 cases, broken down by sex, age, diagnosis, tumour site and sample assay method used.
Safety and Toxicity of Excipients for Paediatrics (STEP)	The STEP database is a free and user-designed resource that collects safety and toxicity information of excipients that is manually extracted from selected information sources. Information submitted to the database is quality controlled externally by SYNFO.

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